

Open Science NL

Open Research Software Advisory Panel

Meeting Agenda

22 September 2025, 15:00 - 17:00 CEST (UTC + 1:00)

Location: MS Teams

Agenda:

- 15.00 - 15.05 – Welcome and agenda
 - Minutes of the last meeting have been published on Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/records/14592058>
- 15.05 – 15.10 - Update on the implementation of the OSNL Work Programme 2024-2025
- 15.10 – 15.20 – Update about the “Metaproject” from those who attended the consultation
 - 15.20 – 15.30 – Q&A
- 15.30 – 16.55 – *Confidential*: Feedback on the draft OSNL Work Programme 2026 – 2027
- 16.55 - 17.00 - Meeting close and plans for the upcoming meeting
 - Meeting 12 December 2025 15.00 – 17.00: Feedback on the draft Work Programme 2026 and 2027
 - Elections of new panel members